

THE RESILIENCE AND ADAPTATION OF DISPLACED PEOPLE BY THE JATIGEDE DAM DEVELOPMENT PROJECT TOWARDS SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOOD

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Abstract

The Jatigede Dam development project has a significant impact on the lives of the surrounding communities. The relocation and substantial changes in social and cultural structures pose challenges that displaced people need to overcome. This research aims to understand the resilience and adaptation of residents affected by the Jatigede Dam development project, focusing on five aspects of resilience communication. The study utilizes a case study approach to delve into the context of the affected community's life. Data collection includes interviews, observations, and document analysis to provide a holistic understanding of the observed phenomena. The results indicate that the affected communities adapt by creating a new normal, strengthening collective identity, maintaining communication networks, and putting alternative logics to work. They also apply alternative logics by focusing on the positive aspects, reducing negative impacts, and creating positive meaning from challenging experiences. The resilience and adaptation of affected communities involve complex and diverse communicative strategies, acknowledging the significant changes in livelihoods and socio-cultural life as integral parts of the adaptation process.

Keywords: Displaced People, Development Project, Resilience Communication, Livelihood.

INTRODUCTION

Large-scale dam development projects, such as the Jatigede Dam in Sumedang, often have significant impacts on the lives of the surrounding communities. The environmental transformation and lifestyle changes resulting from such development demand rapid and sustainable adaptation. In this context, the role of resilience communication becomes crucial in helping residents cope with the occurring changes.

Resilience communication encompasses the ability of individuals or groups to adapt and recover after experiencing changes or crises. In the context of dam development, resilience communication serves as a vital foundation for residents to manage the social, economic, and environmental impacts that arise. Globally, numerous studies have explored resilience communication in the context of environmental changes and the impacts of development. Researchers (Ungar & Hadfield, 2019), in their study titled "The differential impact of environment and resilience on youth outcomes," analyzed the positive and negative influences stemming from various social ecologies on the relationship between resilience levels and behavioral outcomes in youth. The environment, whether familial or scholastic, played a significant role in this complex dynamic. Another study (Javadinejad et al., 2019) titled "Relationship Between Climate Change, Natural Disaster, and Resilience in Rural and Urban

Societies" analyzed individual factors in both rural and urban areas that could affect resilience amid climate change. The research highlighted natural disasters caused by climate change as initially viewed as recurring risks rather than immediate disasters. Each country adopts different management practices to address various hazards, aiming to implement robust programs and reduce risks. The objective of all these management practices is to minimize impact. However, specific studies on the resilience and adaptation of residents affected by dam development projects are still limited.

Therefore, this research extends itself to understand and analyze how resilience communication plays a role in supporting the resilience and adaptation of residents affected by the Jatigede Dam Development Project. Referring to the background and previous research, the main objective of this study is to analyze the role of resilience communication in empowering and adapting residents affected by the Jatigede Dam development project. Through this approach, it is expected that this research can provide in-depth insights into the communicative dynamics occurring in a community facing significant changes.

This study will employ a qualitative approach with a case study research design. Data will be collected through in-depth interviews, participatory focus group discussions (FGD), observational methods, and document analysis. Research participants will be purposively selected, including residents directly affected by the Jatigede Dam development. The study will cover key aspects of resilience communication, such as the role of communication in disseminating information, forming social networks, and managing conflicts. By detailing these factors, effective communication strategies for enhancing community resilience are expected to be identified. This research is expected to provide both practical and theoretical benefits.

Practically, the research findings can serve as a reference for relevant stakeholders, such as local governments and related institutions, in designing responsive empowerment and communication programs tailored to the needs of residents. Theoretically, this research is expected to contribute to the literature on resilience communication, particularly in the context of environmental changes and development.

METHOD

This research adopts a qualitative approach with a case study design as the core method. To gain a deep understanding of resilience communication in the context of changes resulting from the Jatigede Dam development project, the study employs various data collection techniques. The primary methods include in-depth interviews, participatory focus group discussions (FGD), participant observation, and document analysis.

In-depth interviews remain the primary instrument for gaining personal insights from participants regarding their experiences in facing these changes. Meanwhile, FGD serves as an interactive forum involving multiple participants simultaneously, allowing for the exchange of ideas and experiences among affected residents. The benefits of FGD include collaborative participation that can open new dimensions in understanding resilience communication.

Participatory observation allows researchers to directly engage in the daily lives of affected communities. Consequently, the research can capture real-time communicative dynamics and identify changes in communicative interaction patterns.

Document analysis will encompass a review of various sources, such as official project documents, government reports, and media coverage. This will provide additional context and support the qualitative data obtained from interviews, FGD, and observation. Research participants are purposively selected, focusing on residents directly impacted by the Jatigede Dam development. The study was conducted from July to August 2023, allowing researchers to observe and document the dynamics of resilience communication during the crucial period of project implementation. By integrating these various methods, this research aims to present a holistic overview of the role of resilience communication in facing changes induced by the Jatigede Dam development project.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Object Overview Since being designated as the Jatigede Dam Development Zone, the affected population has dispersed to various new locations, including nearby villages. Some have even moved to other districts or experienced transmigration. Being displaced residents poses unique challenges, as they face difficult moments losing connections with family, community, and friends while experiencing the loss of assets and cultural ties.

Traditionally, most communities around the Jatigede Dam relied on agriculture, both in wet and drylands, for their livelihoods. During the relocation, they lost their agricultural and livestock assets, and opportunities to transition to the fisheries or water sectors became limited. This relocation not only affected the economic aspect but also brought about significant social and cultural changes in their lives. Each individual experiencing disruption or a trigger event will react in various ways, with some getting trapped in contaminated narratives, and others getting involved in resilience processes at various levels, either individually or as a family (Scharp et al., 2020).

1. Cipaku Village Situation Before Inundation

The initial situation of the community before inundation reflected a tense and distressing state, with many native residents rejecting the situation. At that time, the Council of Forestry and Environmental Observers of Tatar Sunda (DPKLTS) focused on the social and cultural aspects related to the issue. One primary reason for the rejection was the presence of a historical site, a sacred site, considered a relic of the Sumedang Larang Kingdom, and holding significant value for the Sundanese community in the area (Mariana & Sagita, 2017). Furthermore, DPKLTS assessed that the planning of residents' relocation inadequately considered the cultural aspects inherent in Jatigede community farming. This lack of consideration was considered a major factor in the residents' rejection of relocation. Therefore, DPKLTS emphasized the need for the government to maintain the well-being of the community and involve them more effectively in decision-making processes related to the Jatigede Dam inundation plan. However, eventually, the residents were faced with an urgent situation and

forced to leave their villages immediately. This occurred because heavy machinery had entered the village as part of the preparation for water inundation. The decision to leave the village immediately created an atmosphere of uncertainty and anxiety among the residents, who had to confront the reality of sudden relocation and change in their entire lives. In this context, the community may feel a deep sense of injustice and loss due to sudden and uncontrollable changes, creating new challenges related to adaptation and stability in a new environment.

Figure - Situation of pilgrims to the Lembu Aji Putih tomb before inundation, in Cipaku Village Source: <https://kabuyutancipaku.wordpress.com/>

2. Flooded House Conditions

The swift relocation process created a panic situation among the residents, causing each individual to focus on self-preservation without considering the fate of their neighbors or relatives at that time. The speed of the relocation process and the uncertainty involving rising water levels and a lack of assistance shifted the community's primary focus to personal survival aspects. During those moments, social cooperation and community bonds ceased, illustrating the urgency and complexity of the situation faced by residents in dealing with the threat of water inundation (Ibrahim & Firmansyah, 2019).

Informants admitted that they were confused and limited in their efforts to save their homes. Many residents had not finished moving their belongings when the water continued to rise, with no aid available and transportation costs being high. This expression reflects the real challenges faced by the community, where limited time, lack of assistance, and cost constraints are significant obstacles in maintaining the integrity of their homes amidst the increasing threat of water inundation.

3. Construction of Emergency Houses for New Residences

Forced to undergo urgent relocation, residents were seemingly compelled to save themselves. The simultaneous relocation process forced each individual to face the challenge of building a residence in a new location. This situation created an urgent need to adapt to a new environment, with limited resources in terms of both cost and materials. Concerns about

meeting basic needs such as suitable housing and personal security became the community's primary focus in facing the sudden relocation.

Amidst cost constraints and limited resources, residents were forced to use whatever was available to build new residences with makeshift materials. This condition created significant challenges, especially in maintaining the stability of daily life. Many residents had to work hard to ensure comfort and safety in their new environment. Along with these changes, the community found itself trapped in a situation that not only demanded rapid adaptation but also faced an uncertain future (Budiyanti, 2020).

4. Community Reactions

Relocation becomes a complex issue related to the concept of the location of residence (Eduardo & Murcia, 2019). The displacement of populations due to development, also known as Development-Induced Displacement (DID), can be accepted as part of forced migration occurring when communities or individuals are compelled to leave their residences, often from their places of origin, for economic development purposes. This relocation is associated with long-term construction projects such as dams, roads, and bridges used for general purposes (Sahoo, 2016).

The increasing infrastructure development in developing countries encourages the relocation of residents to new places because such development requires substantial land. The issue of relocation is not easy, as during their stay in their original location, residents do not have the ability to switch to new jobs in the new location. Though financially compensated and supported by other means for their sacrifices following DIDR, the majority of displaced people struggle to rebalance their lives in the new host community (Xi & Hwang, 2011). (Wang et al., 2020). The relocation of residents can cause trauma and pressure when they are in a new place (Khadka & Rinker, 2018).

Additionally, relocated residents sometimes face discriminatory treatment from the original residents, such as in terms of participation in local-level politics (Wang et al., 2020). For the community affected by the Jatigede Dam construction project, 'home' for them includes residence, culture, and identity rooted in a single space (Eduardo & Murcia, 2019). The relocation of residents from the village for the construction of the Jatigede Dam leaves complex problems for the residents, especially the difficulty of adjusting to a new residence and changing jobs. Based on field findings, it was revealed that the local community faced discomfort and anxiety due to difficulties in finding employment.

This reality creates a narrative laden with economic challenges faced by residents. The limited job opportunities become the main cause of uncertainty among them, triggering concerns about economic future and family well-being. This situation also creates significant psychological impacts, presenting deep-seated frustration and anxiety among the local community. Therefore, this issue is not just a concerning economic situation but also a human life story that needs attention in efforts to find solutions and support sustainable development.

The Role of Communication in Building Resilience

The Communication Theory of Resilience (CTR) provides a relevant theoretical foundation for understanding how communities and families can build resilience through communicative processes. In this study, researchers adopt CTR to analyze the findings of a study on residents and families impacted by the Jatigede Development Project in Sumedang, West Java. The main focus of this research is to apply this theory in the context of high-pressure situations, emergencies, or crises related to the impacts of the development project, which often pose complex challenges to communities.

The five communicative processes emphasized by CTR open up a deeper understanding of how communities respond to and mitigate the impacts of the changes they face. These processes involve information exchange, empowerment, social network formation, adaptive skill development, and shared meaning construction. Applying this theory to the context of the Jatigede Dam development project will help identify how communicative interactions of the community can play a key role in building resilience amid inevitable changes.

This research will explore how communities use these communicative processes to face emerging challenges, identify effective communication strategies, and detail the crucial roles played by communities and families in responding to the impacts of the development project. Thus, the application of CTR in this research not only provides a robust theoretical framework but also offers a rich and contextual insight into the communicative dynamics that occur in resilience situations.

Table of Communicative Processes in CTR

No.	Role	Brief Explanation
1.	Crafting New Normalcy	Communicative efforts to maintain previous ways of activities or create new ones amid disruptions, illustrated by global responses like wearing masks during the Covid-19 pandemic and the local community's adaptation to changes caused by the Jatigede Dam development.
2.	Affirming Identity Anchor	Communication to strengthen a specific identity, such as the collective identity of affected residents (OTD) and the reinforcement of individual, institutional, and cultural attributes, including ancestral cultural values.
3.	Using and Maintaining Communication Network	Resilience emerging from interactive processes with family, friends, and societal systems, involving emotional, financial, and practical support to overcome challenges and enhance capacity in facing significant changes.
4.	Putting Alternative Logics to Work	Communicative efforts to reframe pressure situations by adopting new perspectives, exemplified by individuals using alternative logics to view challenges, like military spouses seeing deployment cycles as new 'adventures.'
5.	Legitimizing Negative Feelings while Foregrounding Positive Actions	Communicative efforts focusing on positive aspects amid stress while acknowledging negative feelings, as seen in the community using discourse to shape their realities, emphasizing productive actions and positive aspects in facing significant changes.

1. Crafting New Normalcy

The first process of CTR is 'crafting normalcy,' referring to communicative efforts to either maintain previous ways of performing various activities or create new ways amid disruptions or disasters (Buzzanell, 2010; Venetis et al., 2020). An example illustrating this situation is during the Covid-19 pandemic when people worldwide started wearing masks and practicing social distancing. Traditionally, the majority of communities around the Jatigede Dam were engaged in agriculture, both in wet and drylands. The relocation resulted in the loss of agricultural and livestock assets, limiting opportunities to transition to the fisheries or water sectors.

This process of relocation not only impacted the economic aspect but also brought about significant social and cultural changes in their lives. Individual responses to disruptions or triggering events varied, with some getting trapped in contaminated narratives, while others engaged in resilience processes at various levels, both individually and as families. Overall, the concept of Crafting New Normalcy reflects the community's adaptive efforts to the changes they face and their understanding of the complexity of the challenges encountered.

2. Affirming Identity Anchor

The second process is 'affirming identity anchor,' referring to communicative efforts to strengthen or enhance a particular identity (Chernichky-Karcher et al., 2019). This identity may manifest both overtly and covertly, continued by individuals and groups experiencing various forms of traumatic conditions or disasters. In this study, the identity anchor is categorized as individual, institutional, and cultural attributes proven to be reliable sources of support during difficult times, such as the label of Affected People (Orang Terkena Dampak - OTD), becoming the collective identity of displaced residents due to the Jatigede Dam Development.

Individual attributes include the unique experiences and characteristics of each person in the affected community, while institutions refer to organizations or social structures that support and articulate shared identity. Culture, as the third component, becomes a strong foundation for collective identity and can function as a strong anchor in challenging situations. The ancestral Sundanese culture is a significant aspect of understanding the identity of the affected community.

Their concern that dam construction could disconnect them from their cultural roots adds a specific dimension to the efforts of 'affirming identity anchor.' Ancestral culture reflects the heritage, traditions, and values passed down from generation to generation. When the community worries about being cut off from their ancestral cultural roots, it indicates the crucial role of this aspect in shaping their identity.

The process of 'affirming identity anchor' becomes a manifestation of the communicative resilience of the affected community. They not only reinforce individual, institutional, and cultural attributes but also attach ancestral cultural values as an integral part of their identity. Thus, the community strives to preserve and respect their cultural heritage, facing the threat of change resulting from dam construction.

3. Using and Maintaining Communication Network

Resilience emerges from interactive processes across various functional levels, including social interaction with family, friends, or societal systems (Brown & Westaway, 2011; Masten & Obradović, 2006). Resilience results from interactive processes involving various levels of functionality in daily life. For the residents impacted by the Jatigede Dam construction, resilience becomes crucial in facing significant changes in their environment. This interactive process includes social interactions involving family, friends, and societal systems. It is essential to understand that resilience is not only individual but also stems from social support and engagement in a solid communication network.

In social interaction with family, affected residents receive emotional, financial, and practical support that helps them overcome challenges arising from relocation and environmental changes. This support creates a framework that supports mental and emotional resilience. Moreover, interactions with peers can provide a different channel of support. In difficult situations, peers can be a source of unique emotional support, considering they may have experienced or understood similar situations.

This social engagement facilitates the exchange of experiences and adaptive strategies, strengthening solidarity among the affected. Societal systems, such as local organizations, community groups, or institutions supporting affected residents, also play a crucial role in enhancing resilience. Support from the local community can come in the form of assistance programs, adaptation training, or facilitating access to necessary resources.

Active participation in community life can strengthen a sense of ownership and involvement, which, in turn, can enhance the capacity of individuals and families to cope with change. Therefore, the resilience of the Jatigede Dam-affected residents does not only arise from individual resilience but also from interactive processes with the social and societal environment. Support from family, peers, and the local community forms a mutually supportive network, enabling the community to be more resilient in facing the challenges of change.

4. Putting Alternative Logics to Work

The fourth process refers to communicative efforts to reframe pressure situations in ways that do not neglect the stress itself (Lillie et al., 2018; Chernichky-Karcher et al., 2019). Applying alternative logics involves adopting new ways of viewing difficulties that encompass the existence of negative aspects.

These ways are called alternative logics because they may show something contrary to intuition or desire, yet can help individuals understand challenges. For instance, spouses of military personnel may use alternative logic by viewing the instability created by their spouse's deployment cycle as a new 'adventure' (Villagran et al., 2013). Individuals apply these alternative logics by using them to perceive and communicate about challenging situations.

5. Legitimizing Negative Feelings while Foregrounding Positive Actions

This stage refers to communicative efforts to focus on the positive aspects of a stressful situation while also working to reduce the negative aspects (Chernichky-Karcher et al., 2019; Lillie et al., 2018). Legitimizing negative feelings while foregrounding productive actions involves recognizing that although negative emotions are necessary, they are unproductive; in other words, instead of dwelling on negative things, individuals should focus on the positive aspects of their situation and make progress or maintain optimism (Lillie et al., 2018; Venetis et al., 2020).

Through various discourses, communities actively shape their realities and express how those realities give meaning to their life experiences. Emotions, as something 'intersubjective,' are the result or product of how meaning systems are created and negotiated among humans, with interactional context as a guide for emotional expression. Although their discourse about losing homes does not always show 'negotiation' occurring over time, residents can provide insights into the creation of individual, family, and community meaning at a particular point in time. Thus, the emotional perspective not only provides a discourse-centered approach to the loss of assets and jobs but also insights into how individuals, families, and communities mutually develop rules, narratives, and 'codes for emotional appropriateness' (Buzzanell & Turner, 2003).

Residents affected by the Jatigede Dam development strive to build resilience through communicative efforts focused on the positive aspects of their situation. In the context of dam construction, where there is pressure and negative feelings emerging, the community takes the initiative to mitigate these negative impacts. These efforts include legitimizing negative feelings, but more importantly, emphasizing productive actions and focusing on the positive aspects of their situation.

This strategy aligns with the view that directing attention toward progress, optimism, and solutions can help manage the emotional burdens arising from challenging situations, such as relocation due to development. To uplift their psychological conditions, discourse is needed to shape reality and meaning for the affected community. Discourse here is used as a tool to express feelings and give meaning to their life experiences. Although there isn't always negotiation seen in the discourse related to losing homes, the community can still provide an overview of meaning creation at a specific point in time. This reflects how they, as individuals, families, and communities, actively develop narratives, rules, and codes for their emotional appropriateness.

In the context of relocation, this shows that the community is not only focusing on the loss of physical assets but also depicting how they formulate emotional meanings surrounding it. Residents affected by the Jatigede Dam Development use communication as a means to manage feelings, understand their realities, and formulate meaning in the face of significant changes in their lives. By emphasizing positive and productive aspects, as well as through discourse that creates meaning, the community strives to build emotional and social resilience in confronting challenging conditions.

CONCLUSION

The empowerment and adaptation of residents affected by the Jatigede Dam development project demonstrate five main aspects:

1. **Crafting New Normalcy:** The community adapts by creating a new normal. Proactive communication is evident in efforts to maintain old practices and create new ways to face changes. Awareness of significant changes in livelihoods and socio-cultural life is acknowledged as an integral part of this adaptation process.
2. **Affirming Identity Anchor:** The affected residents strengthen their identity through communicative efforts. Collective identity, manifested in the term "Orang Terkena Dampak (OTD)" (People Affected), becomes a strong anchor for community resilience. Their connection to Sundanese ancestral culture highlights the crucial role of concerns about losing cultural roots in shaping identity.
3. **Using and Maintaining Communication Network:** Community resilience emerges through social interaction with family, friends, and the broader community. Maintaining communication networks is key to coping with the pressures of change. Communication serves not only as a practical tool but also as a means to form emotional and social connections that support sustainable living.
4. **Putting Alternative Logics to Work:** Involves communicative efforts to reframe views of stressful situations by applying alternative logics. This includes adopting new ways of perceiving difficulties, enabling individuals to understand and communicate about challenging situations in a more positive and productive manner.
5. **Applying Alternative Logics and Focusing on Positive Aspects:** The efforts of the affected community to embrace the positive aspects of challenging situations are reflected in the process of applying alternative logics. This strategy helps minimize negative impacts, acknowledges negative feelings, and encourages a focus on productive actions and positive aspects of the situation. The community strives to create positive meaning from the difficult experiences they face.

Overall, these communicative processes play a crucial role in enhancing the resilience and adaptation of residents affected by the Jatigede Dam development project. The community actively engages in communicative strategies to navigate and make sense of the significant changes in their lives, emphasizing the importance of understanding and addressing the complex challenges posed by development projects.

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